

Face Mask Detection Using CNN and Transfer Learning: An Experimental Evaluation

Paul Onyekachi Onyekwelu, with the collaboration of Chisom Queendarlyn Eze

Abstract

Automated face mask detection has emerged as an important computer vision application in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, helping enforce public health guidelines in crowded spaces. This study presents the implementation and experimental evaluation of a face mask detection framework using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and transfer learning techniques. A custom baseline CNN model and four pre-trained architecture, which includes ResNet-50, VGG19, InceptionV3, and Xception, were developed and evaluated on a balanced dataset of masked and unmasked face images.

The models were trained using a consistent experimental setup and assessed using standard classification metrics, including Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. The results demonstrate that transfer learning significantly enhances performance compared to training a CNN from scratch. Among the evaluated architectures, Xception achieved the highest accuracy and generalization ability, while the baseline CNN also delivered competitive results.

This work highlights the potential of deep learning approaches for accurate and efficient face mask detection and provides insights into the relative strengths of popular CNN architectures. Future work will focus on optimizing model robustness through hyperparameter tuning, data augmentation, and exploring ensemble techniques for deployment in real-world scenarios.

Keywords: Face Mask Detection, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Transfer Learning, Deep Learning, Image Classification, Computer Vision

Data Availability Statement

The dataset used in this study is publicly available on Kaggle at <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/belsonraja/face-mask-dataset-with-and-without-mask>. All data used for training and evaluation were obtained from this open-source repository and are freely accessible for research and educational purposes. No proprietary or restricted datasets were used in this study.

1.0 Introduction

The global COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the critical importance of wearing face masks in public spaces to reduce viral transmission, however, ensuring compliance with mask mandates in densely populated areas remains a significant challenge. (Ghadekar et al., 2021; Hearne & Niño, 2022). In response, automated face mask detection has emerged as a vital application of computer vision, a subfield of Artificial Intelligence (AI), that enables machines to interpret and process visual data in a manner similar to human vision (IBM, 2023).

Face mask detection typically involves identifying human faces in an image or video stream and determining whether the detected individuals are wearing masks. This is formulated as a binary classification problem within the broader domain of object detection (Das et al., 2020). Automated approaches reduce the burden on manual surveillance and help enforce public health guidelines more efficiently.

Recent advances in deep learning, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have demonstrated remarkable success in image recognition tasks. CNNs can learn hierarchical representations directly from image data, eliminating the need for manual feature engineering (Islam et al., 2020). Additionally, the use of transfer learning, leveraging pre-trained models such as ResNet-50, VGG19, InceptionV3, and Xception, enables the development of high-performance models even when working with relatively limited datasets (Kamal & Ez-Zahraouy, 2023; Vihar, 2020; Tsang, 2019).

This study aims to develop and evaluate a computer vision framework for face mask detection by comparing the performance of a custom-designed CNN model against several pre-trained architectures. The goal is to determine which models most effectively distinguish between masked and unmasked individuals in visual data. Through this evaluation, the project seeks to inform the design of accurate and efficient systems that can support public health monitoring in real-world environments.

The specific objectives of this research are:

- To implement a custom CNN architecture for binary face mask classification.
- To build and fine-tune models using pre-trained weights (ResNet-50, VGG19, InceptionV3, and Xception) via transfer learning.
- To evaluate and compare model performance using standard classification metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score.
- To identify the most effective model for real-world face mask detection based on empirical results.

2.0 Related Work

Deep learning techniques, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have transformed the field of computer vision in recent years, achieving state-of-the-art performance in object detection and image classification tasks (IBM, 2023). The global COVID-19 pandemic further motivated researchers to explore these capabilities for practical applications such as automated face mask detection (Islam et al., 2020).

A variety of methods have been proposed for face mask detection. Das et al. (2020) developed a simplified CNN-based architecture for face mask classification, achieving accuracies of up

to 95.77% and 94.58% across different datasets. Ghadekar et al. (2021) designed a Keras-based model that outperformed MobileNetV2 and VGG16, reporting a precision of 99% and an F1-score of 98%. Similarly, Munjal et al. (2021) implemented a real-time face mask detection system using a CNN trained on a dataset of 4000 images, achieving an accuracy of 98%.

Transfer learning approaches have also been successfully applied. Eyiokur et al. (2023) constructed a high-performing face mask and face-hand interaction detection system using various pre-trained models. Their study highlighted the advantage of leveraging deep networks for robust real-time detection under unconstrained conditions.

Despite these promising results, several gaps remain. Many studies focus on specific architectures or configurations, and relatively few perform a direct, systematic comparison of multiple CNN architectures under a controlled experimental setup. As noted by Yang & Shami (2020), the optimal choice of architecture and hyperparameter tuning remains an open research problem for face mask detection. Furthermore, while some prior works utilized transfer learning, comprehensive comparisons between custom-designed CNN models and transfer-learned models such as ResNet-50, VGG19, InceptionV3, and Xception are still limited.

This study addresses this gap by systematically comparing the performance of a baseline CNN with several popular pre-trained architectures using identical training conditions and evaluation metrics. By doing so, it aims to provide new insights into the relative strengths and weaknesses of different deep learning approaches for face mask detection.

3.0 Methodology

The methodology encompassed the data loading and pre-processing, model selection, design and construction, training processes, and model evaluation (figure 1).

Figure 1: Project Flow Diagram

3.1 Data Description and Pre-processing

The dataset used in this study was obtained from a publicly available repository on Kaggle. It comprises a total of 3000 images, evenly distributed across two classes: With Mask and Without Mask. The images represent a diverse range of individuals captured under varying lighting conditions, backgrounds, and facial orientations. This diversity provides a realistic and challenging basis for evaluating the generalizability of the models.

Prior to model training, several pre-processing steps were applied to the dataset to ensure consistency and improve the efficiency of the learning process. First, all images were resized

to 224×224 pixels with three colour channels (RGB). This resolution was chosen both to match the input size requirements of the pre-trained architectures used in this study and to optimize computational performance.

Next, Pixel values were rescaled to the range [0,1] to stabilize the training process and improve convergence.. In addition, the training and validation subsets of the dataset were cached in memory to minimize disk access latency during the training phase. To enhance the robustness of the training process, the training data were shuffled with a buffer size of 1000, ensuring that mini-batches presented to the model during each epoch were drawn from a randomized sequence of examples. Finally, the dataset was split into two subsets: 80% for training and 20% for validation.

Figure 2: A sample of images in the Dataset. (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

3.2 Baseline CNN Model

To establish a performance baseline for face mask detection, a custom CNN model was implemented using TensorFlow and Keras. The model follows a sequential architecture comprising convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers for binary classification. The network begins with an input layer that rescales pixel values to the range [0, 1] to improve training convergence. It then applies three convolutional blocks, each consisting of a convolutional layer with increasing filter sizes, followed by a ReLU activation and max-pooling to down-sample feature maps while preserving salient features. The resulting feature maps are flattened and passed to a fully connected dense layer with a 50% dropout rate for regularization. The final output layer uses a sigmoid activation to perform binary classification, predicting the probability that an input image depicts a masked or unmasked face (Figure 3).

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Model: "sequential"

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Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
rescaling (Rescaling)	(None, 224, 224, 3)	0
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 224, 224, 32)	896
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 112, 112, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 64)	18496
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 56, 56, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 56, 56, 128)	73856
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 28, 28, 128)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 100352)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	12845184
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	129

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Total params: 12,938,561
Trainable params: 12,938,561
Non-trainable params: 0

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Figure 3: Baseline Model Summary (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

3.3 Transfer Learning Models

To complement the custom baseline CNN model, this study investigates the performance of four pre-trained deep learning architectures: ResNet-50, VGG19, InceptionV3, and Xception. These architectures are well-established in image classification tasks and have demonstrated strong performance in various domains. Each architecture was adapted for the binary face mask detection task using a transfer learning approach.

3.4 Model Training Procedure

All models were trained using a consistent training procedure to ensure a fair comparative analysis. The dataset was divided into 80% training and 20% validation subsets. Training was conducted using the Adam optimizer. The learning rate was set to 0.001, and the batch size was fixed at 32 samples per iteration. The models were trained to minimize the binary cross-entropy loss. The training process was configured to run for a maximum of 10 epochs. To prevent overfitting and promote generalization, an Early-Stopping callback was employed, which terminated training if the validation loss did not improve for five consecutive epochs.

3.5 Evaluation Metrics

The models were evaluated using the standard evaluation metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. These metrics collectively provide insights into both the overall classification performance and the balance between sensitivity and specificity of the models. Mathematically, they are evaluated as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

The classification outcomes are defined as follows:

- True Positive (TP): Instances where the model correctly predicts the positive class.
- False Positive (FP): Instances where the model incorrectly predicts the positive class.
- True Negative (TN): Instances where the model correctly predicts the negative class.
- False Negative (FN): Instances where the model incorrectly predicts the negative class.

4.0 Results

Tables 1 and 2 summarize the classification reports and performance of each model.

Table 1: Classification Report of the different Models

Model	Binary Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Baseline Model	0 (Masked)	0.97	0.96	0.96
	1 (Unmasked)	0.96	0.97	0.96
ResNet50	0	0.92	0.99	0.96
	1	0.99	0.92	0.95
VGG19	0	0.95	0.94	0.94
	1	0.94	0.95	0.95
InceptionV3	0	0.76	1.00	0.87
	1	1.00	0.70	0.82
Xception	0	1.00	0.99	0.99
	1	0.99	1.00	1.00

Table 2: Validation and Training Accuracies and Losses of the different Models

Models	Training		Validation	
	Accuracy (%)	Loss	Accuracy (%)	Loss
Baseline Model	98.83	0.04	96.33	0.13
ResNet50	98.5	0.04	95.50	0.29
VGG19	94.92	0.19	94.50	0.18
InceptionV3	99.33	0.02	84.67	0.57
Xception	100.00	0.0001	99.50	0.008

4.1 Baseline CNN Model

The baseline CNN model demonstrated balanced performance across all evaluation metrics. It achieved a training accuracy of 98.83% and a validation accuracy of 96.33%, with corresponding training and validation losses of 0.04 and 0.13, respectively. The model exhibited strong Precision and Recall for both classes, resulting in an overall F1-Score of 0.96 for both masked and unmasked faces. The confusion matrix (Figure 4) confirms that the model performs well in distinguishing between the two classes.

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix of the Baseline Model. (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

Figure 5: Accuracy and Loss plot of the Baseline Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

4.2 ResNet-50

The ResNet-50 model achieved a training accuracy of 98.5% and a validation accuracy of 95.50%, with training and validation losses of 0.04 and 0.29, respectively. It demonstrated high

Precision (0.99) and Recall (0.92) for the unmasked class, and slightly lower Precision (0.92) for the masked class. The confusion matrix (Figure 6) highlights this asymmetry.

Figure 6: Confusion Matrix of the ResNet50 Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

Figure 7: Accuracy and Loss Plot of the ResNet50 Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

4.3 VGG19

The VGG19 model produced a training accuracy of 94.92% and a validation accuracy of 94.50%. The corresponding training and validation losses were 0.19 and 0.18, respectively. The model maintained balanced Precision, Recall, and F1-Score across both classes, achieving solid performance overall. The low difference between training and validation losses indicates that VGG19 generalized well to unseen data.

Figure 8: Confusion Matrix of VGG19 Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

Figure 9: Accuracy and Loss plot of VGG19 Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

4.4 InceptionV3

InceptionV3 achieved a perfect Recall of 1.00 for the masked class but at the cost of lower Precision and Recall for the unmasked class. Its training accuracy was 99.33%, while its validation accuracy dropped to 84.67%. The training and validation losses were 0.02 and 0.57, respectively. While the InceptionV3 model was able to learn the training data effectively, its generalization to unseen data was limited (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Confusion Matrix of InceptionV3 Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

Figure 11: Accuracy and Loss Plot of InceptionV3 Model. (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

4.5 Xception

The Xception model achieved the highest performance among all evaluated architectures. It reached a perfect training accuracy of 100% and a validation accuracy of 99.50%, with training and validation losses of 0.0001 and 0.008, respectively. The model attained near-perfect Precision and Recall for both classes, with an F1-Score of 1.00 for unmasked faces and 0.99 for masked faces. The confusion matrix (Figure 12) confirms this well-balanced and robust performance. Despite the near-perfect training performance, the slight gap in validation accuracy suggests some degree of memorization, though this was minimal compared to other models.

Figure 12: Confusion Matrix of Xception Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

Figure 13: Accuracy and Loss Plot of Xception Model (Source : Personal Jupyter Notebook)

5.0 Discussion

The results presented in Section 4 demonstrate that both the custom CNN model and the pre-trained architectures achieved high levels of performance in detecting whether individuals were wearing face masks. However, distinct differences were observed in their generalization capabilities, training dynamics, and robustness.

The baseline CNN model exhibited strong overall performance, achieving a validation accuracy of 96.33% and maintaining balanced precision, recall, and F1-Score across both classes. Its relatively simple architecture allowed for fast convergence while still capturing relevant features. However, a small performance gap between training and validation accuracy, as well as slightly higher validation loss, suggests the presence of mild overfitting.

Among the pre-trained models, Xception delivered the best overall results, achieving a near-perfect validation accuracy of 99.5%, balanced precision and recall, and minimal loss. Its architecture, based on depth-wise separable convolutions, appears particularly effective for this task. However, the model achieved a perfect training accuracy of 100%, which suggests some degree of overfitting or memorization of the training data (Tsang, 2019).

ResNet-50 and VGG19 also performed well, achieving validation accuracies of 95.5% and 94.5% respectively. ResNet-50 benefitted from its use of residual connections, which likely helped it extract deeper features. However, similar to the baseline model, both ResNet-50 and VGG19 exhibited slight discrepancies between training and validation performance.

In contrast, InceptionV3 showed signs of more pronounced overfitting. While it achieved a very high training accuracy (99.33%), its validation accuracy dropped to 84.67%, with corresponding instability in precision and recall. This suggests that InceptionV3 may be less suited to smaller datasets of this type without additional regularization or data augmentation (Vihar, 2020). Overall, the results indicate that pre-trained models, especially Xception and ResNet-50, can offer substantial gains in accuracy and feature extraction capabilities compared to a custom CNN, even when trained on a relatively small dataset.

6.0 Conclusion and Future Work

This study presented the implementation and evaluation of a computer vision-based face mask detection framework using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The results demonstrate that deep learning models, particularly those leveraging transfer learning, are capable of achieving high accuracy in face mask detection tasks. Among the models evaluated, Xception exhibited the highest overall performance, while the baseline CNN also achieved competitive results, highlighting the potential of simpler architectures when properly designed and trained. However, the risk of overfitting remains an important consideration, particularly for deeper architectures. The use of Early-Stopping and dropout regularization partially mitigated this risk, but future work could explore additional strategies such as more aggressive data augmentation or fine-tuning of learning rates. One limitation of the present study is the size of the dataset. Although the dataset was balanced and diverse, larger and more varied datasets would likely improve generalization and robustness in real-world applications. Additionally, incorporating data augmentation techniques could further enhance model performance and reduce overfitting.

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